

Emissions and power system: Optimizing the development of electricity production in Argentina

Agustín Forquera, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina; Luis Giussani, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina
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Executive Summary

In order to accomplish the 2030 Agenda Objectives, Argentina must transform its energy matrix to ensure sustainability while maintaining supply security.

Using OSEMOSYS, three scenarios are modeled: **Baseline** (fossil fuel dominance), **20% Renewables** (meeting Law 27.191 targets), and **Carbon Tax** (32.5 USD/tCO₂). Results show that even with strong renewable policies, natural gas remains dominant, accounting for at least 53% of generation by 2050. Without intervention, its share would rise to 83%. The carbon tax scenario boosts renewables to 41% but increases system costs.

To achieve decarbonization, Argentina must modernize its grid, invest in energy storage, and implement incentives for renewables. Its high solar potential could address seasonal peaks, but greater flexibility is needed.

1. Introduction

In the context of the [2030 Agenda](#) (Consejo Nacional de Coordinación de políticas Sociales, 2020), Argentina faces the challenge of transforming its energy matrix to meet two key objectives: ensuring universal access to affordable, reliable, and modern energy services and significantly increasing the share of renewable energy in the overall energy mix. To achieve this, electricity system planning must consider both supply security and environmental sustainability.

In this study we aim to answer three questions; What would be the impact of continuing the trend of our current energy matrix? Is it profitable to invest in renewable energy in a context where natural gas is so cheap? And what would be the effect of a carbon tax?

2. Methodology

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To explore possible paths for energy planning, this report uses OSEMOSSYS as a long-term linear programming optimizer. Data is collected from official sources such as CAMMESA (www.cammesa.com/informes-y-estadisticas/) and the Energy department (www.datos.gob.ar). The assumptions include increasing energy demand and decreasing costs of renewable energy. Three scenarios will be considered: a **Baseline Scenario**, representing the evolution of the Argentine power system without significant policy or investment changes, assuming continued demand growth with a predominant reliance on fossil fuels and limited renewable energy integration; a **Renewable Energy Floor Scenario**, based on Argentina’s Electric Energy Law 27.191 (www.argentina.gob.ar/normativa/nacional/ley-27191-253626), which mandates that renewable power generation (with the exclusion of big hydroelectric power plants) must account for at least 20% of total electricity production; and a **Carbon Tax Scenario**, exploring the impact of a carbon pricing mechanism on the electricity mix, assessing how an additional cost on fossil fuel emissions could incentivize the transition toward cleaner energy sources and influence overall system costs, investments, and electricity prices.

Figure 1. Analyzed scenarios

3. Results

The projected increase in total electricity generation remains consistent across all scenarios, reaching 135% between 2021 and 2050. This growth reflects the anticipated rise in electricity demand and underscores the need for long-term energy planning strategies to ensure supply security and sustainability.

Natural gas continues to be the predominant energy source in all scenarios due to its relatively low cost and well-established infrastructure. In the Base scenario, its share in electricity generation follows an increasing trend, reaching 83% by 2050, highlighting its economic competitiveness in the absence of policy-driven incentives for renewable energy. In contrast, the Carbon Tax scenario leads to a reduced reliance on natural gas, with its share declining to 53% as renewable energy sources gain a larger role in the energy mix.

Figure 2. Electricity generation (PJ)

The total system cost varies across scenarios, reflecting the economic impact of different energy policies. The Base scenario incurs the lowest cost at 325,877 million USD, benefiting from the continued use of low-cost fossil fuels without additional environmental regulations. The Carbon Tax scenario, which introduces a 32.5 USD/tCO₂ penalty on emissions (average social cost estimated)¹, results in the highest cost at 333,800.66 million USD, due to the need for investment in cleaner technologies and the added expense of carbon pricing. The Renewable 20% scenario represents an intermediate approach, with a total cost of 328,144 million USD, as it encourages renewable deployment while still relying on fossil fuels for system stability.

Figure 3. Total Costs (billions of USD)

¹ This value represents the Social Cost of the emissions. (INTEGRATION OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN CHILEAN PUBLIC INVESTMENT, www.piappem.org)

Emissions outcomes vary significantly depending on the scenario. The Base scenario leads to the highest CO₂ emissions, reaching 8,136 million tons by 2050, due to the continued dominance of fossil fuels. The Carbon Tax scenario achieves the most substantial emissions reduction, lowering total emissions to 7,624 million tons, as the additional cost of carbon incentivizes a shift toward cleaner energy sources. The Renewable 20% scenario results in a moderate emissions reduction to 7,735 million tons, facilitated by increased wind and solar power generation, though natural gas remains a significant contributor.

Figure 4. Total Emission (MMTCO₂/Year)

5. Discussion

Following the decarbonisation paths in Argentina requires a substantial transformation, balancing its abundant natural gas reserves with an accelerated expansion of renewable energy. If the current energy matrix trend continues, natural gas will remain the dominant source due to its low relative costs, leading to high emissions and long-term dependence on fossil fuels. This trajectory raises concerns regarding environmental sustainability and energy security, as reliance on a single resource may expose the system to price volatility and supply disruptions.

A key question is whether investing in renewable energy is profitable given the affordability of natural gas. While fossil fuels currently provide a cost advantage, long-term economic and environmental factors must be considered. The decreasing costs of wind and solar power, coupled with financial incentives and policy mechanisms, can improve their competitiveness. Expanding renewable capacity—primarily wind and

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solar—alongside grid modernization and energy storage solutions will be essential to enhance system reliability, reduce emissions, and ensure diversification.

The implementation of a carbon tax could significantly alter the cost structure of the energy sector, making renewables more competitive by internalizing the environmental costs of fossil fuel consumption. Policy mechanisms such as carbon pricing adjustments, renewable auctions, and financial incentives for wind and solar deployment will be crucial in driving this transition. Given Argentina's high solar potential, solar PV can play a critical role in addressing seasonal demand peaks, particularly in summer.

However, for renewables to reach a greater share of the energy mix, grid flexibility measures and investment in energy storage technologies are necessary. A key limitation of this study was not modelling the Argentinian North West (NOA) region separately, which does not fully capture the constraints on electricity transmission between regions. These limitations highlight the need for further research on grid expansion and the integration of high-renewable scenarios.

Future research should focus on developing a multiregional model to capture transportation costs, local price differences, and regional productivity variations, allowing for a more precise assessment of energy distribution efficiencies and highlighting economic disparities across regions. Additionally, increasing temporal segmentation will enable better analysis of seasonal, weekly, and daily energy demand fluctuations, providing more accurate insights into peak demand periods and grid stability issues. Another crucial area of study is assessing system stress conditions, including dry periods and low-wind hours, to minimize the risk of non-supply by evaluating the resilience of the energy system under extreme weather conditions and ensuring backup mechanisms are in place.

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